

Application of Bunnett Criterion in Mixed Aqueous Solvents. Part II. A Kinetic Study of the Base Catalysed Decomposition of Diacetone Alcohol in DMSO-Water Mixtures*

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The kinetics of the base catalysed decomposition of diacetone alcohol at a fixed concentration of 0.01M NaOH was studied in DMSO—water mixtures of varying compositions. The rate of this reaction was found to be enhanced in the presence of increasing amounts of DMSO. Plots of $\log k-H_-$ or $\log (k/C_{OH^-})$ against $\log a_{H_2O}$ were found to be linear with slopes of 7.5 and -4.0 respectively. Application of Bunnett's hydration hypothesis was attempted and is shown to be consistent with the B-1 mechanism postulated for this reaction on the basis of other evidences.

IN continuation of our earlier work on this subject¹, we undertook a kinetic investigation of the base-catalysed decomposition of diacetone alcohol in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO)—water mixtures of varying compositions to study the applicability of Bunnett criteria to mechanistic elucidation in these mixtures.

Experimental

A B.D.H.(L.R.) grade sample of DMSO was cooled in ice water and frozen at about 5°. The supernatant liquid was decanted off, and the solid melted and distilled under a pressure of 8 mm. The middle fraction boiling at 63° at this pressure was collected and stored out of contact with air. Double distilled water was employed in the preparation of DMSO—water mixtures. Diacetone alcohol was purified by distilling under a pressure of 17 to 18 mm and the fraction boiling at 78° to 79° was collected and stored.

2,4,3'-trinitrodiphenylamine, 2,4-dinitrodiphenylamine, 2,4-dinitro-4'-aminodiphenylamine and 4-nitrodiphenylamine were used as indicators for the determination of H_- and were prepared according to standard methods².

H_- measurements : H_- is defined by

$$H_- = pK_a^W + \log \frac{C_{B^-}}{C_{BH}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where pK_a^W is the negative logarithm of the thermodynamic dissociation constant of the indicator referred to the infinitely dilute solution in water. C_{B^-}/C_{BH} is the indicator ratio given by

$$\frac{C_{B^-}}{C_{BH}} = \frac{D-D_{BH}}{D_{B^-}-D} \quad \dots (2)$$

where D denotes the optical density of the experimental solution, and D_{BH} and D_{B^-} those of the indicator in the unionised and the ionised form respectively, all the measurements being made at the same concentration of the indicator at a definite wavelength. Further details have been published earlier³. The reliability of H_- data at any composition was always tested by using two overlapping indicators.

Kinetic measurements : —

A dilatometric method^{4,5} was employed for following the rate of decomposition of diacetone alcohol at 30°. The rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the plots of $\log (h_\infty - h_t)$ against time in the various mixtures where h_∞ and h_t correspond to the height at infinite time and that at any time t respectively.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data and the H_- data in the various DMSO-water mixtures are presented in Table I together with the activities of water at these compositions taken from the work of Cox and Metigue⁶. Considering a B-1 mechanism such as

where SH is the substrate and X^\ddagger is a kinetic intermediate and assuming that the step following the initial proton abstraction as rate determining and

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth Anniversary.

TABLE I—RATE CONSTANTS AND H_- DATA IN DMSO—WATER MIXTURES

Temp : 30° ;	Conc. of NaOH : 0.01M ;	Conc. of Diacetone alcohol : 0.1M ;			
Mole % DMSO	First order Rate const. k_1 in min ⁻¹	H_-	$\log(k/cOH^-)$	$\log k-H_-$	$\log a_{H_2O}$
2.72	9.908×10^{-3}	12.45	-0.004	-14.45	-0.023
5.92	1.376×10^{-2}	12.80	+0.14	-14.66	-0.043
9.73	2.607×10^{-2}	13.25	+0.42	-14.83	-0.071
14.36	3.310×10^{-2}	13.80	+0.52	-15.28	-0.017
20.10	4.613×10^{-2}	14.45	+0.66	-15.79	-0.171
27.39	1.089×10^{-1}	15.30	+1.04	-16.26	-0.261

applying the Bronsted's equation for the effects of changing medium on the rate determining step,

$$-\frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_1 \frac{C_s^- f_s^-}{f_{\ddagger}^-}$$

In the above equation k_1 is the rate coefficient for the rate determining step, and f_s^- and f_{\ddagger}^- are the activity coefficients of the conjugate base of the substrate and the transition state respectively. Substituting for C_s^- in terms of the equilibrium constant, K_e ($K_e = K_{SH}/K_W$) of step (1) of the reaction scheme, and considering the indicator equilibrium

and using the relation

$$h_- = \frac{f_B^-}{f_{BH}} \cdot \frac{K_W \cdot a_{H_2O}}{a_{OH^-}} \quad \dots (4)$$

we get

$$\log k_{obs} = \log(k_1 \cdot K_{SH}) + \log \frac{f_s^- \cdot f_B^-}{f_{\ddagger}^- \cdot f_{BH}} + H_- \quad \dots (5)$$

Hence, a plot of $\log k_{obs}$ against H_- should be linear, if the activity coefficient ratio remains more or less constant, equal to zero or a linear function of H_- with changing medium,—a condition which may possibly, though not necessarily, be approximated because of the symmetrical nature of the activity coefficient term in equation (5). These arguments hold under conditions when the change in the number of water molecules associated with the ionisation of the indicators in basic solution is the same as the change in the number of water molecules involved in the ionisation of the substrate in the kinetic experiments. In a general case, assuming that " n_2 " is the change in the number of water molecules associated with the indicator ionisation in basic solutions and " n_1 " is the change in the number of water molecules associated with the transformation of the substrate to the transition state, equation (5) can be modified as

$$\log k_{obs} = \log \frac{f_{SH}^- \cdot f_B^-}{f_{BH} \cdot f_{\ddagger}^-} + \log(k_1 \cdot K_{SH}) + H_- - (n_1 - n) \log a_{H_2O} \quad \dots (6) \text{ or,}$$

Equation (6) shows that a plot of $\log k_{obs}$ against H_- is not necessarily linear because the activity of water varies with the medium. Moreover O' Ferrall and Ridd⁷ noted that a plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs. H_- for the methanolysis of chloroform is not linear in the concentration range

1M <NaOMe> 3M in agreement with equation (6).

Applying the Bunnett hydration hypothesis, the B-1 mechanism can be written as

s, n, p and t represent the hydration numbers of the various species given in the above equations. The transformation of the deprotonated substrate to the transition state may take place through one step as written or a series of rapid equilibria followed by one rate determining step.

Summing up (7) and (8) gives

where K_e represents the equilibrium constant for the formation of the transition state. Thus

$$-\frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_1 C_{\ddagger(H_2O)_t} \quad \dots (10)$$

Expressing the concentration of the transition state in terms of K_e , the rate constant may be written as

$$k_{obs} = k_1 \cdot K_e \cdot C_{OH^-} \cdot a_{H_2O}^{(t-s-n-1)} \cdot \frac{f_{SH}^* \cdot f_{OH^-}^*}{f_{\ddagger}^*} \quad \dots (11)$$

Fig. 1 Decomposition of Diacetone Alcohol in DMSO-Water Mixtures. Plot of $\log(k/C_{OH^-})$ (Curve 1) and $-(\log k-H_{-})$ (Curve 2) Against Log Activity of Water.

$$\log(k_{obs}/C_{OH^-}) = \text{constant} + (t-s-n-1)\log a_{H_2O} + \log \frac{f_{SH}^* \cdot f_{OH^-}^*}{f_{\ddagger}^*} \quad \dots (12)$$

The activity coefficients and C_{OH^-} in equations (11) and (12) represent those of the hydrated species.

A plot of $\log(k_{obs}/C_{OH^-})$ against $\log a_{H_2O}$ (Fig. 1) should be linear if the activity coefficient term remains reasonably constant with changing medium. The slope of the linear plot (Fig. 1) is -4.0 , so that

$$t-s-n-1 = -4.0 \text{ or } s+t-n-t = 3.0 \quad \dots (13)$$

This value suggests that the initial state consisting of the substrate and the hydroxyl ion is more hydrated than the transition state. This may not be unreasonable in view of the fact that the initial state has a high negative charge density (on OH^- ion) as well as a hydratable functional group whereas the transition state has a dispersed charge. It is also seen from Fig. 1 that a plot of $\log k-H_{-}$ versus $\log a_{H_2O}$ is linear with the slope $(t-s)-(a-b) = 7.5$. In this equation a and b refer to the hydration numbers of the indicator acid and anion respectively while t and s have their usual significance. The classification of base catalysed reactions into B-1 and B-2 classes on the basis of the magnitudes of the slopes corresponding to the two types of plot from Fig. 1 analogous to the acid catalysed reactions must, however, await systematic studies of a large number of base catalysed reactions. Increase in the rate of this reaction on the addition of DMSO most possibly arises, from the increased activity of the hydroxide ion due to its desolvation in the presence of increasing amounts of DMSO. The recent work by Das and Kundu⁸ on the standard free energy of transfer of the hydroxyl ion from water to DMSO-water mixtures is particularly relevant in this context. Increase in the rates of

many reactions⁹ involving anions in the presence of DMSO has been reported earlier⁹, and other factors such as ion-dipole, dipole-dipole interactions and the mutual polarisability of the reacting partners in the transition state may also contribute to the increase in rate.

Two mechanisms have been proposed (B-1 and B-2) for this reaction of which the B-1 mechanism has been favoured¹⁰ on several grounds. This is consistent with the conclusions arrived at above from the application of the Bunnett hydration hypothesis which, in spite of its limitations, offers a useful pragmatic basis for mechanistic studies of acid and base catalysed reactions.

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Fig. 1. Decomposition of diacetone alcohol in DMSO-water mixtures. Plot of $\log(k/C_{OH^-})$ (Curve 1) and $-\log(k-H_{-})$ (Curve 2) against log activity of water.